

SPIRITUAL AND MENTAL PREPARATION OF THE POPULATION FOR EMERGENCIES

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Annotation: Psychology also plays an important role in the protection of Labor. In modern production, the problem of accidents, injuries is not solved only by engineering methods. From experience it is known that accidents and injuries occur on the basis of deficiencies in the work of the engineer-constructor. It also causes organizational and psychological reasons, for example, low preparation for safety requirements by profession, inadequate training, neglect of security measures by specialists, involvement of persons who do not have sufficient qualifications for risky work, exhausting people at work and being in a psychological state. These reduce the distrust (security) of a specialist's activities. In this article, opinions and comments about the spiritual preparation of the population for emergency situations are made.

Keywords: Ensuring the safety of citizens, spiritual preparation, emergency situations, spiritual preparation for emergencies, loyalty to the ideas of national independence.

Many studies show that approximately 15-20 percent of people during disasters are able to behave, correctly assess the situation and act according to the situation. The behavior of the rest is quite predictable, natural, but, unfortunately, it cannot be called rational. The behavior of these people is associated with mental changes that arise due to the shock of the incident that occurred. International experience has shown that 60-90% of the damage from household production occurs due to the fault of the affected persons, according to the research. Security psychology represents the introduction of psychological knowledge in ensuring the safety of activities. Here, the types of psychological states that appear in the process of labor activity are thoroughly examined, psychological processes, psychological characteristics are considered. Negative processes occurring in the human psyche are eliminated in training with the help of special specialists in effective positive methods. Psychological risk also has a very strong impact in terms of exposure because it has a managerial nature.

The decision of the Cabinet of Ministers in order to improve the system of protection of Population and territories in Uzbekistan from natural and technological emergencies is one of the main measures that provide the

population with the knowledge of action in these situations in order to prevent technical and emergency risks that may occur today, as well as protection measures are taken.

This decision provides for all the effects that affect life security. In addition, the Republic of Uzbekistan on the Prevention of emergency situations and further improvement of the state system of action in such situations, the assignment of new tasks to the Ministry of emergency situations, the Prevention of emergency situations and the development of regulations on the state system of action in such situations and aimed at preventing possible risks of all kinds

The functions of the local government bodies in the territorial subsystem of the state system for their prevention and action in emergency situations are defined as the functions for the protection of the population and territories from emergency situations, aimed at ensuring the safe conduct of the lifestyle and life activity of the population, the functions of the population in the process We can say with confidence that these measures carried out in our country aimed at creating paradise - like conditions, which are far from the risks in our country, by our government and the president of our country. This is done by the president of our republic. Sh. Mirziyoyev believes that "since we have strength, courage in our body -we will create the best conditions necessary for our people, our people have always been worthy and worthy of such excess", we can see the above decisions, proof of reforms. A word about security measures security measures this is the implementation of practical, organizational, material defense of methods and bases.

When preparing for emergency situations, the following are considered important:

- Create a material and technical base to eliminate emergencies;
- Providing insurance assistance to the affected population from natural disasters;
- Training of all strata of the population in preparation for emergency situations and their elimination;
- Organization and equipment of sanitary posts, initiative groups on emergency situations among young people;
- Preparation of disaster prevention groups among community volunteers and employees;
- Water sanitation and water supply in emergency situations;
- Restoration of family ties in emergency situations;
- International cooperation in the field of emergency situations;

- To prepare for emergency situations at all levels and develop plans for their elimination.

In the process of carrying out work on eliminating the consequences of an emergency, rescuers are in contact with the population in the disaster zone. In such conditions, extreme conditions affect the mood of people. In the zone of emergency, there are two groups of factors that cause damage to the psyche of people.

The first group includes factors associated with the presence of a physical threat to human life and health. Among them are explosions, fires, collapse of buildings and structures, radioactive pollution, pollution of the external environment with chemical dangerous substances, toxic products, etc. Mental disorders caused by their effects are observed mainly against a physiological (medical) background. conditions including injuries, burns, radiation injuries, chemical poisoning, pain and traumatic shock.

The factors of the second group are associated with the scale and consequences of emergency situations, the degree of threat to people's lives and health, the lack of reliable information about the fate of relatives and loved ones, changes in the habitual way of life. , the feeling of weakness in front of uncertainty about the situation and the future. It is not possible to completely eliminate or neutralize the influence of Psycho-traumatic factors in both groups on an individual in the process of work on the elimination of an emergency, but through the provision of systemic psychological and psychological assistance. social work can significantly increase the psychological resistance of people with victims to these effects. In order to provide psychological support to the victims, rescuers need to know how the most typical mental disorders of people develop and persist in emergency situations, how to distinguish them from each other by signs, and how to provide assistance in a particular case. Currently, there are three main periods of emergency development, during which the victims experience a variety of mental disorders.

In addition, the Cabinet of Ministers adopted a decision “on improving the procedure for preparing the population for emergency action and in the field of citizen protection”. According to him, the regulation on the procedure for preparing all segments of the population for emergency action and in the field of citizen protection was approved. It is also important to ensure that the heads of State Government, Local executive authorities and other organizations, workers and employees are able to prevent and eliminate emergencies and consistently improve their knowledge and skills in Citizen Protection.

In conclusion, the rescue services and rescue structures, as well as the structures of The Citizen Protection, will be prepared for the elimination of emergency situations. Protection of the population, including those who are not employed in the sphere of production and service, educators of preschool institutions, students of general secondary schools, students of secondary special, vocational and higher education institutions in emergency situations, providing first aid to the victims, the rules and methods of using collective and personal protective equipment are taught.

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